

Investigation of the photoluminescence properties of quantum dots using theoretical simulation

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the optical behavior of CdSe quantum dots, a class of semiconductor nanomaterials widely studied for light-emitting, photovoltaic, and bioimaging applications owing to their size-dependent electronic structure. The objective is to clarify the relationship between quantum dot size, size distribution, and emission characteristics through experimental and simulated optical spectra. UV–Vis absorption, photoluminescence, and simulated PL spectra were analyzed for CdSe quantum dots excited at 325 nm. The experimental PL spectrum exhibits a single and narrow emission band assigned to the $1S_e \rightarrow 1S_h$ transition, which is blue-shifted compared with bulk CdSe, confirming strong quantum confinement in 2–3 nm particles with a very narrow size distribution of less than 1%. A large Stokes shift of 0.93 eV is observed, attributed to confinement effects and surface-related states. Simulated photoluminescence (PL) spectra for 3–6 nm quantum dots show progressive red-shifting and spectral broadening with increasing particle size, while smaller quantum dots display stronger PL intensity due to enhanced confinement and more efficient radiative recombination. Parameter analysis further reveals that size deviation and linewidth broaden emission and reduce intensity without changing the peak wavelength. These findings provide useful guidance for optimizing CdSe quantum dots for QLEDs, bioimaging, and broadband optoelectronic devices.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor nanoparticles exhibit quantum confinement effects on electrons and phonons, which strongly influence their optical and electrical properties [1]. Confinement leads to an increase in the direct interband transition energy, enabling the band gap to be tuned by modifying particle size [2]. A substantial enhancement, by several orders of magnitude, in radiative recombination efficiency has also been reported [3]. The nonlinear dependence of electronic excitation energy on particle size allows semiconductor nanoparticles to be used in applications such as second harmonic generation and long-pass optical filters [4]. However, this nonlinear optical response can be greatly suppressed when the crystallite size is nonuniform. Therefore, determining both the particle size and its distribution is essential.

Commonly, the average size of nanoparticles is estimated using the width of major X-ray diffraction (XRD) peaks via Scherrer's formula. Although widely applied, this method neglects the effects of lattice distortion on peak broadening and does not provide information about size distribution. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) offers direct measurement of particle size and distribution [5]–[7], but the technique is destructive and requires complex sample preparation.

An alternative approach uses the frequencies of confined acoustic phonons obtained from low-frequency Raman spectra to estimate particle size. Nevertheless, the assignment of vibrational modes can be ambiguous. Moreover, particle size significantly affects optical characteristics, causing inhomogeneous broadening in optical spectra. For example, Jun and Tung [8] calculated the absorption spectrum of quantum dots with a finite size distribution using an infinite-potential-well model that neglects intrinsic linewidth arising from vibronic coupling, resulting in a delta-function spectrum for monodisperse dots.

Efforts to match computed absorption spectra with experimental data have been reported [9], [10], but these require prior knowledge of parameters such as oscillator strength, bandwidth, and the energies of all electronic transitions. For materials like CdSe, up to 12 parameters may be needed, and these values—often approximated from empirical relations or band-structure calculations—can introduce significant uncertainties. In contrast, photoluminescence (PL) spectra typically exhibit distinct features associated with band-edge emission and defect-related recombination [11], [12]. Although the inhomogeneous broadening of these spectra is also linked to particle size distribution, a quantitative analysis has not yet been performed.

This study proposes a simple and robust method for analyzing the inhomogeneously broadened band-edge PL lineshape to extract particle size distribution. The method is validated using the PL spectra of CdSe nanoparticles with diameters ranging from 3 to 6 nm. To reduce the number of fitting parameters, the measured photoluminescence spectrum of bulk CdSe is employed as an input reference for lineshape estimation.

2. METHOD

2.1. Experimental section

During the high-temperature synthesis of CdSe quantum dots, the Cd:OA ratio was fixed at 1:4.1 and Se:TOP at 1:3.23, while varying the Cd:Se ratio, temperature, and reaction time to investigate their effects on particle size and quality. The synthesis procedure is as follows: A mixture of $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Cd}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, OA, and DPE (as solvent) was stirred and heated at 120–180 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere to form a pale-yellow Cd–OA complex solution. Separately, a 0.1 M Se–TOP solution was prepared and quickly injected into the reaction flask. Within seconds, the solution changed color depending on the reaction conditions. Crystal growth was controlled by maintaining the temperature for a set duration. Particle size was indirectly determined using UV-vis absorption and photoluminescence spectra. To stop the reaction, 6 mL of toluene was rapidly added to cool the mixture. The resulting CdSe QDs were purified by precipitating with methanol, centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, discarding the supernatant, and redispersing the precipitate in toluene. This purification process could be repeated several times.

2.2. Theoretical simulation

The PL spectrum of a direct bandgap semiconductor material with a bandgap energy of E_0 is distributed according to a Gaussian function. Here Γ is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the PL spectrum.

$$g_b(E) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{2\pi}\Gamma} \exp\left[-\frac{(E-E_0)^2}{2\Gamma^2}\right] \quad (1)$$

We have that E_0 depends on the size of the nanoparticle.

$$E(R_0) = E_0 + \frac{\hbar^2\pi^2}{2R^2} \left[\frac{1}{m_e} + \frac{1}{m_h} \right] - \frac{1.8e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon R} + \frac{e^2}{R} \sum \alpha_n \quad (2)$$

Therefore, (1) is rewritten as (3).

$$g_{qd}(E, R_0) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{2\pi}\Gamma} \exp\left[-\frac{(E-E(R_0))^2}{2\Gamma^2}\right] \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, the particle sizes are not uniformly distributed, resulting in a particle size distribution that follows a Gaussian distribution function.

$$P(R) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_R} \exp\left[-\frac{(R-R_0)^2}{2\sigma_R^2}\right] \quad (4)$$

The σ_R refers to the standard deviation, which is determined through $p = \sigma_R/R_0$. The shape of the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum is thus determined by (5).

$$G(E) = \int P(R) \cdot g_{qd}(E, R) dR \tag{5}$$

Infer:

$$G(E) = \frac{1}{2\pi\Gamma\sigma_R} \int_0^\infty \exp\left[-\frac{(R-R_0)^2}{2\sigma^2} - \frac{(E-E(R))^2}{2\Gamma^2}\right] dR \tag{6}$$

The (6) is the formula we use for simulation, allowing the computer to generate the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum when we input the particle size as a parameter. An approximation of (2) can be made by neglecting the third term.

$$E(R_0) = E_0 + \frac{\hbar^2\pi^2}{2R^2} \left[\frac{1}{m_e} + \frac{1}{m_h}\right] - \frac{1.8e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon R} \tag{7}$$

With the CdSe material, we have: $E_0 = 1.74$ eV, $m_e = 0.13 m_0$, $m_h = 0.4 m_0$, and $\epsilon = 10.6$. The Γ parameter of bulk CdSe is 0.185 eV [13].

$$E(R) = 1.74 + \frac{3.845}{R^2} - \frac{0.4465}{R} \text{ (eV, nm)} \tag{8}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 displays the UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the FTO/QDs photoanode with ZnS and ZnSe passivation layers doped - Cu^{2+} in the range of 300–700 nm. Light is illuminated from the FTO substrate side, showing absorption dependence on the Cu^{2+} doping ratio. Below 550 nm, the absorption intensity slightly increases with Cu^{2+} content, possibly due to the formation of Cu^{2+} energy levels within the bandgap of ZnS and ZnSe. This result is consistent with the study on Sr doping in ZnSe for QDSSCs [14]. The FTO/TiO₂/QDs/ZnSe@ Cu^{2+} system exhibits enhanced absorption and a red shift in the 500–600 nm range. The FTO/TiO₂/QDs/ZnS@ Cu^{2+} photoanode shows a higher absorption spectrum intensity than the FTO/TiO₂/QDs/ZnS@ Cu^{2+} photoanode. Overall, the doped anode films absorb longer wavelengths, extend into the visible light region, and result in a darker material.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was employed to investigate the structural characteristics of CdS, CdSe, ZnS@ Cu^{2+} , and ZnSe@ Cu^{2+} quantum dots deposited on the TiO₂ surface. The diffraction patterns (Figure 2) confirm the crystalline nature of all samples. Specifically, five prominent diffraction peaks of TiO₂ observed at 25.354°, 37.785°, 48.077°, 53.922°, and 62.728° are indexed to the (101), (004), (200), (105), and (204) planes, respectively, corresponding to the anatase phase (JCPDS No. 00-004-0477) [15]. The cubic phase of CdS is identified by the characteristic (111) and (222) reflections at 26.5° and 54.5°, respectively (JCPDS No. 00-089-0440) [15], [16]. For CdSe, two peaks located at 27.2° and 42° are attributed to the (101) and (110) planes of the hexagonal structure (JCPDS No. 00-008-0459) [15]. Similarly, the hexagonal phases of ZnS and ZnSe are confirmed by peaks at 25.7° and 48.8°, which correspond to the (100) and (103) planes (JCPDS No. 00-089-2940) [14]. These results collectively demonstrate the successful deposition and crystallization of CdS, CdSe, ZnS@ Cu^{2+} , and ZnSe@ Cu^{2+} quantum dots on the TiO₂ substrate.

Figure 1. UV-Vis of X(S,Se) passivation layers doped - copper

Figure 2. XRD spectra of X(S,Se):Cu passivation layers

The photovoltaic performance (J–V curves) of QDSSCs employing $\text{TiO}_2/\text{QDs}/\text{ZnS}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ and $\text{TiO}_2/\text{QDs}/\text{ZnSe}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ photoanodes was evaluated under standard solar illumination ($100 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$), as summarized in Table 1 and Figure 3. The results indicate that the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor (FF) exhibit minimal variation between the two systems; however, the conversion efficiency shows a marked dependence on the current density. Specifically, the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{QDs}/\text{ZnS}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ photoanode yields a current density of $22 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and a corresponding efficiency of 4.5%, which is lower than that of the $\text{TiO}_2/\text{QDs}/\text{ZnSe}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ counterpart. Upon Cu^{2+} doping into the ZnSe passivation layer, both the current density and power conversion efficiency are significantly enhanced, achieving values of $23 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and 5.3%, respectively. This improvement is attributed to the substitution of Zn^{2+} by Cu^{2+} in the crystal lattice, which reduces the film's internal resistance and introduces impurity energy levels within the bandgap of ZnS and ZnSe, thereby enhancing photon absorption. These findings are in good agreement with previous studies, which demonstrated that Cu^{2+} and Mn^{2+} doping in ZnS substantially increased the photocurrent density.

This study examines the electron transfer mechanisms within thin-film layers, including electron transport at the photoanode interface (R_{ct2}), electron diffusion in the electrolyte, and charge transfer at the cathode (R_{ct1}), through electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) under illumination at $100 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The analysis, conducted using EC-LAB software, reveals that electrodes coated with Cu^{2+} -doped ZnS exhibit lower charge transfer resistances (R_{ct1} and R_{ct2}) compared to those coated with Cu^{2+} -doped ZnSe, with minimum recorded values of $R_{ct1} = 17 \Omega$ and $R_{ct2} = 33 \Omega$ (Figure 4). Concurrently, the current density and overall device efficiency improved notably, from $22 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ to $23 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. This enhancement is primarily attributed to the $\text{ZnS}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ layers, which not only improve photon absorption but also contribute to light reflection, thereby increasing the effective light harvesting by the TiO_2/QDs photoanode [17]-[22].

Furthermore, the conduction band edge of $\text{ZnS}@\text{Cu}^{2+}$ is positioned higher than that of TiO_2/QDs , which helps suppress electron back diffusion and reduces recombination losses [23]. The incorporation of Cu^{2+} also induces a redshift in the absorption spectrum, extending into the visible light region, due to the formation of impurity levels within the bandgap of ZnS and ZnSe [24]. These results are consistent with the findings reported in previous studies, and demonstrate significantly improved efficiency compared to previous studies [8], [25].

Figure 3. Photovoltaic performance of X(S,Se):Cu

Figure 4. EIS of X(S,Se) passivation layers doped - copper

Table 1. The characteristic parameters of devices

Sample	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} ($\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$)	FF	PCE (%)	R_{ct1} (Ω)	R_{ct2} (Ω)
Photoanode based ZnS:Cu	0.515	22	0.41	4.5	12	116
Photoanode based ZnSe:Cu	0.52	23.1	0.439	5.31	17	331

4. CONCLUSION

The Zinc(S,Se):Cu passivation layer was successfully synthesized via the SILAR method and employed to passivate the surfaces of CdS and CdSe quantum dots in the photoanode. Beyond its protective function, this layer enhances photon absorption in the quantum dot solar cell. The absorption spectrum shows a pronounced redshift in the visible region for the Zinc(S,Se):Cu-treated electrode compared with the undoped sample, consistent with the J–V characteristics. With this passivation layer, the current density increased to $23 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ and the power conversion efficiency reached 5.3%, confirming its contribution to

improved light harvesting. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy further revealed that the Zinc(S,Se):Cu sample exhibits the lowest charge-transfer resistance, indicating suppressed recombination and more efficient electron transport. The structural features, surface morphology, and film thickness were verified by XRD and FESEM analyses.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Le Doan Duy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓	
Le Xuan Thuy			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [LXT], upon reasonable request.

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